

POPULATION GROWTH, RESOURCES AND ENVIRONMENT : AN OVERVIEW-BANGLADESH PERSPECTIVE

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INTRODUCTION.

Population growth, depletion of resources, environmental degradation and pollution are interlocking parts of an overall crisis. There is no denying the fact that 'people over population' is the main cause of resource depletion and environmental crisis, especially in the developing countries. Where as in developed countries, 'consumption over population' is the major contributor. It's easily perceivable that any increase in the size of population increases the per-capita resource consumption as well as environmental degradation and pollution per unit of resource used which constitute overall environmental impact. (Miller, 1991 : 14). The International Development Strategy for the Third United Nations Development Decade, adopted by the General Assembly in December, 1980, as well as other review, studies and strategies, have identified population, along with resources and environment, as three vitally important areas of concern to mankind in the remaining years of this century and beyond. In this paper, an attempt has been made to examine the relationship between population growth, resources and environment with special emphasis on Bangladesh which occupies the 8th position in world ranking in terms of the size of population. In other words, the overall impact of population growth on the eco-systems will be examined.

DEGRADING ECO-SYSTEM.

As we know, an eco-system is the combination of biological community and the chemical and physical factor making up its non-living environment. The eco-systems which are the focal point of environmental concern include terrestrial eco-system (land resources), aquatic eco-system (water resources) and atmospheric eco-system (air). The components of these eco-systems and their pollutants are briefly described below.

Terristrial Eco-system (Land Resources).

Land resources may be divided into four groups : (1) productive land, (2) cropland topsoil, (3) forest cover and, (4) grass land. The environmental issues regarding land resources are desertification, deforestation, covering production land with concrete, building etc, topsoil erosion, land erosion, water logging, salinization, declining wild life habitats etc. At the same time, main pullutants of land may be classified into five groups; (1) domestic wastes, (2) non judicious use of chemical fertilizers and insecticide, (3) metal (Cadmium, Zinc, lead, copper, Nickel etc.) (4) solid waste material and (5) radioactive waste.

Aquatic Eco-system (Water Resources).

Main components of aquatic eco-system are, ponds, lakes, rivers, ocean, coral reefs, estuaries and coastal and inland wetlands (Swamps, marshes etc.). The materials that are considered main water pullutants include pathogenic materials, sediments, excess heat, inorganic chemicals and mineral substances, oxygen demanding wastes, acids and bases, radioactive materials, petroleum, disease causing agents and synthetic organic compounds.

Atmospheric Eco-system (Air).

Air is mainly polluted by large factories, chemical plants, oil refineries, metal smelting and recovering works, electric power station, transportation sector and space heating and cooling systems. Airborne contaminants include among other things dust, fly ash, smoke, soot, aerosol, gases and vapours resulting from dust producing processes, combustion, manufacturing processes, agricultural activities, solvent and nuclear energy activities. The ultimate effects of air pollution are climatic changes, global warming and ozone depletion which affect adversely the living organisms and materials. In fact, all human activities have some impact on the environmental resources.

ENVIRONMENTAL RESOURCES.

Let us now examine the components of environmental resources. Resources are of three types, namely, perpetual, non-renewable and renewable. Perpetual resources include direct solar energy, winds, ocean water etc. which are virtually inexhaustible. Renewable resources include fresh air, fresh water, fertile soil, plants and are replanished through natural process. But, many a time, a renewable resource may be converted into a

non-renewable one from prolonged and improper use or due to pollution. Environmental degradation starts whenever the highest use rate exceeds the natural replacement rate.

Non-renewable resources include fossil fuel like coal, oil, natural gas etc, metallic minerals like iron, copper etc, and non-metallic minerals like clay, sand, phosphate etc. These types of resources may be recycled or re-used. management of natural resources is very important because we are rapidly exhausting our non-renewable resources, degrading the potentially renewable resources and threatening even the perpetual resources. It demands immediate attention, especially in third world countries, where only scarce resources are available for an enormous size of population. Resource scarcity and population boom are directly linked with poverty and causing economic and social chaos as it is being observed in the sub-Saharan countries of Africa.

The health report on non-renewable world resources is not encouraging. The USA has officially designated the following materials as critical or vulnerable : In the first tier come chromium, manganese, cobalt and PGMs etc. and in the second tier-antimony, cobalt, molybdenum, nickel, niobium, titanium etc. Let us examine the picture of molybdenum and nickel only. According to world statistics of 1979—81, molybdenum's production was 1,07,667 tonnes. Demand growth 4.5% per annum, static reserve life only 45 years where as the depletion rate by the year 2100 is 249%. In case of nickel the production is 7,19,000 tonnes, demand growth 04%, static reserve base 76 years and depletion rate 152% (Turner, 1990).

The condition of potentially renewable resources is also alarming. About 8.1 million square km of land (croplands, forests and grass lands) have become deserts in the last 50 years. Fertile top soil is degrading quickly due to topsoil erosion, salt build up, water logging, and thus reducing the crop productivity significantly. Almost half the world's tropical forest have already been cleared and the clearing and degrading process is still on. One third of the world's wetlands have either been lost or seriously polluted. The Ocean is the largest trash dump. Waters of thousand of lakes and rivers is so acidic that these are without fish. A majority of the people living in the rural areas of LDCs do not have access to safe drinking water. The pollution of atmospheric eco-system is bringing climatic change, causing disruption in food production and flooding low lying areas like Bangladesh and thousands of species of plants and animals becoming extinct each year. It is estimated that about 10 million people have lost their home and land because of environmental degradation (Miller, 1991 : 11). Magnitude of the environmental problem caused by population growth is examined below.

CONSEQUENCES OF POPULATION GROWTH :

World population is increasing exponentially. Doubling the world population needed less than 40 years when it rose upto 5.3 billion in 1992 from 2.5 billion in 1950.

Table-1 **World Population**

	Population (in million)			Population growth Rate (%)	
	1960	1992	2000	1960— 1992	1992— 2000
1. All Developing Countries	2070	4240	4930	2.2	1.9
2. Industrial Countries	930	1210	1400	0.8	0.6
3. World	3000	5450	6330	1.8	1.6
4. Bangladesh	51.4	119.5	144.3	2.7	2.4

Source : UNDP, Human Development Report 1990.

It's evident from table 1 that world population have increased by 1.8% over the period 1960—92 and will increase by 1.6% over the period 1992—2000 assuming CBR, CDR and CPR remain the same. Demographic transition to stabilized population is far away. The UN has currently projected that the world population will ultimately stabilize at 11.6 billion shortly after the year 2200, compared with stabilization at 10.2 billion in 2100 put forth in the 1982 projection with 97% of global population growth occurring in the developing countries (UN 1993).

Food And Nutrition

Human beings need food and nutrition for their survival, and increase in population creates demand for more food and nutrition. Sources of food energy has been shown in the following table.

Table-2 Sources of Human Food Energy

Food	% of energy supplied	
Cereals :		
Rice	21	
Wheat	20	
Corn	05	
Others	10	56
Roots and tubers :		
Potatoes and yams	05	
Cassava	02	07
Fruits, Nuts and vegetables		10
Sugar		07
Fats and oils		09
Livestock Products and fish		11
		100

Source : Ehrlich, Ehrlich and Holdren, 1977.

So we see that except for fish all the food and energy resources including the livestock are directly or indirectly related to land. Environmental impact of population growth on land resources may be summarized as below :

- deforestation,
- overgrazing of grass lands,
- plowing of grass lands,
- soil erosion,
- depletion of top soil due to intensive cropping,
- depletion of soil due to inappropriate use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides,
- pollution of ground water through use of pesticides and herbicides,
- release of toxic substances into the soil,
- loss of bio-diversity through conversion of forest cover to agriculture,
- encroachment of agriculture into the forest land,
- destroying wild life habitat,
- salinization due to unregulated shrimp culture in the coastal areas,
- urbanization causing loss of agricultural land,
- irrigation, drainage and flood control measures causing
 - i) water logging,
 - ii) siltation,
 - iii) erosion of river banks,
 - iv) over exploitation of ground water affecting the eco-system adversely,
 - v) damaging the top soil through use of polluted surface water, and
 - vi) introduction of unwanted species like weeds and diseases into the crop land.

In today's world, according to some estimates, about 40% of the population of the developing countries are undernourished and another 40% are malnourished.

Against this backdrop, population of the third world countries is expected to increase by 1.9% annually needing more human activities for food and nutrition. A few years back, it was believed that technology is capable of facing the challenge. Now it is evident that technological change-induced agriculture is unable to cope up with the rapid population growth. At the same time, the prospect of raising food supply and nutritional levels in the developing countries has dimmed.

According to UNDP, if adequate food for all the world's expanding population is to be produced, the present rate of loss or degradation of agricultural land can not be continued. Over grazing, excessive cultivation, unwise irrigation, urbanization, solution to the many complex problems of soil deterioration and loss, and the permanent damage to the agricultural base of food production which the process entails, will vary from one continent, country, region and locality to another, but while the sustainable management of any agro-eco-system must be a matter of sound husbandry, based on adequate scientific knowledge related to the particular local environment, a wider global perspective is necessary. (El-Hinnawi and Hashmi, 1982).

The Bangladesh population has increased by 2.17% over the period 1981—1991. Bangladesh Bureau of statistics (BBS) has projected Bangladesh population, under variant mode of fertility and mortality changes, as follows.

Table : 3 **Range of Projected Population**

End Year of Projection	Minimum Population (million)	Maximum Population (million)
2006	132.45	149.49
2011	142.61	163.46
2016	153.82	176.16
2021	161.13	185.54

Source : BBS, 1994.

As it is shown in Table-3, 50 to 74 million more people will be added to the Bangladesh population by the year 2021 (Taking 1991 as the base year.). This means that Bangladesh has to grow more food and nutritional produces on the same land available today. This can be done by—

- (a) increasing cropping intensity,
- (b) using high yielding variety (HYV) seeds,
- (c) applying chemical fertilizers,
- (d) using pesticides and herbicides and
- (e) extending irrigation, drainage and flood control measures.

There is no doubt that the extension of any of the above measures will affect the environment considerably. Unless appropriate planning is made today, we are certainly going to jeopardise the terrestrial eco-system of the country.

Health and Water.

Population growth generates demand for health services, water and sanitation facilities. According to UNDP, in case of LDCs, percentage (%) of population with access to health services is 54 for the period 1985—91, to safe water is 45 for the period 1988—91 and to sanitation is 32 for the same period. In 1992, 250 million people of the LDCs did not have access to services, 330 million to safe water and 370 million to sanitation. There was only one doctor to serve 19,110 people (UNDP 1994). So most people are naturally susceptible to water related diseases like dysentery, diarrhoeal diseases, hepatitis, typhoid, paratyphoid, conjunctivities, scabies, malaria, yellow fever, schistosomiasis etc.

Health, water and sanitation services are most vital for healthy and productive population. But access to these services is very limited in present day. More people have access to health services than water and sanitation services (see table-4). As a result, they survive but are not healthy enough to contribute significantly towards national development.

Table : 4 Rural Population With Access To Services (%).

Country	Rural population as % of total 1992	Health (85—91)	Water (88—91)	Sanitation (88—91)
Pakistan	67	85	45	10
Zimbabwe	70	80	14	22
Zambia	58	50	28	12
Nigeria	63	62	30	05

Source : UNDP, 1994.

The position of Bangladesh in this regard is not satisfactory at all. The factors responsible for poor health and sanitation condition are as follows :

- low literacy rate,
- poverty and malnutrition,
- inadequate and inefficient health and family planning services,
- lack of supervision and control over the health personnel,
- inadequate supply of sanitary materials,
- inadequate supply of drinking water especially in the urban areas,
- creation of urban slums/squatters,
- lowering of ground water level,
- pollution of ground as well as surface water, and
- inadequate human and industrial waste disposal facilities etc.

Bangladesh is a riverine country and as such, water is available every where but not round the year. Often we do not realize the quantum of water we need to survive. (see table-5). It may be observed that the biggest sector using water is irrigation. Although the requirement of drinking water is comparatively less but its importance certainly can not be ignored.

Table : 5 **Some Water Requirements.**

Use	Amount of Water Used (m ³)
Drinking Water (adult, daily)	0.001
Toilet	0.02
Clothes Washing	0.17
Refine a ton of Petroleum	2—50
Produce a ton of finished steel	6—270
Grow a ton of wheat	300—500
Grow a ton of Rice	1500—2000
Produce a ton of milk	10,000
Produce a ton of beef	20,000—50,000

Note : M³ = 1000 Litre = 264 Gal ; 01Ton = 1000Kg.

Source : J. Hirschleifer, J. Dettaven, and J. Milliman, (1969 : 27).

While population growth increases water requirements, simultaneously it adds to water pollution. Sustainability of water supply, sanitation and health services can not be achieved without enhancing the over all socio-economic condition of the masses. However, continual efforts must be made to improve the situation. In fact, Bangladesh has achieved considerable success in providing safe drinking water to the rural people.

Energy Consumption.

Energy plays a crucial role in sustaining the life-support system of our planet. Infact, The real economic system is dependent on the extraction of large quantities of matter from the environment, processing and converting them into various forms, culminating in final products for consumption. (Ayres and knesse, 1989). Needless to say, without energy all human activities will come to a standstill, More people means more human acitivities

and enhanced energy consumption. Annual per-capita energy consumption in 1973 of selected countries have been shown in Table-6.

Table : 6 Energy Consumption in Selected Countries (1973).

Country	Annual per Capita energy consumption (mj)
U.S.A	3,44,000
Swedan	1,76,000
U.K.	1,66,000
West Germany	1,67,000
Japan	1,04,000
Argentina	55,000
China	15,300
India	5,400
Indonesia	3,800
Nigeria	1,900

Note : 01 Mega Joule (MJ) = 239 kilo calories (kcal)

Source : Ehrlich, Ehrlich and Holdren, 1970.

It's evident from the data that developed countries are consuming most of the world energy. In fact, they account for about 66% of world energy production and about 85% of world consumption (World Bank, 1979).

The Environmental concern regarding energy encompass pollution of the eco-system as well as degradation of the non-renewable resource base. Enviromental impacts of energy production and consumption include the following :

- marine oil pollution,
- sulphur oxides and nitrogen oxides emissions causing acid rain,
- concentration of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere,

- threat of nuclear radiation on man,
- operational safety and reliability of nuclear reactors,
- handling and disposal of radio-active-wastes,
- nuclear proliferation causing 'damaging effects' to the eco-system,
- depletion of fossil fuel (coal, natural gas, oil etc.),
- emission of trace contaminants like ash particles, mercury and other heavy metals (in coal and petroleum.),
- loss of soil and vegetation,
- desertification and
- depletion of forest resources etc.

In Bangladesh, the energy scenario is completely different from other countries of the world. Here, fossil fuel and electricity (in other words-commercial energy) contribute only 26.9% and biomass fuels contribute 73.1% to the total energy consumption. Again agricultural residues contribute 63.5% and fuel wood 17.65% to the total biomass fuel supply. Moreover, 81% of total bio-mass fuel was consumed for domestic cooking of which the consumption for rural and urban cooking were 64.5% and 16.5% respectively. (Sobhan, 1991 : 53) Thus, Bangladesh is silently heading towards a serious energy crisis causing irreparable damage to the environment. Rapid population growth is increasing the problem exponentially.

Transport and Industry.

Transport and industry constitute a very significant position in human activities. With increasing trend in economic development, the problem is compounding day by day. The main environmental concern of this sector may be summarized as below.

- increased motorized traffic is causing congestion in the roads resulting in lower vehicle speed and demand for road development,
- construction of roads, airports, railways, pipeline etc. causing depletion of land resources,
- disturbing wild life habitats,
- noise pollution,
- increased accident causing loss of life and property,
- air pollution,

- industrialisation attracts labour from rural areas and thus creates urban slum,
- industrial wastes polluting the water and top soil and
- human health is adversely affected by industries in residential areas.

Urbanization.

Urbanization is a cumulative effect of population growth, imbalanced development policies and rural poverty. In most of the LDCs socio-economic development is urban biased. Vast rural areas are deprived of modern amenities of life as well as capacity to absorb more people. So poverty stricken rural people are migrating to urban areas in search of employment opportunities.

In developed countries, urbanization is 73% as compared to 32% of that in LDCs which are experiencing rapid population growth as well as urban growth. It has been projected that by 2020 almost two thirds of the world's population will be living in urban areas. Accomodating 2.9 billion people more in urban areas by 2020 will be a monumental task. (Miller, 1991 : 125). A greater part of this urbanization will take place in LDCs where cities are already struggling to manage their present population.

Bangladesh is experiencing rapid urbanization as shown in the following table.

Table : 7 Growth Rate of Urban Population (1901—1991) :

Year	Population (%)	Average annual growth rate (exponential)
1901	2.43	..
1911	2.55	1.39
1921	2.64	0.85
1931	3.02	2.00
1941	3.66	3.59
1951	4.33	1.69
1961	5.19	3.75
1971	8.78	6.62
1981	15.18	10.63
1991	20.15	5.43

Source : BBS, 1994.

Environmental impacts of urbanization include the following :

- Increase of slums/squatters.
- Increase of urban poor.
- Inadequate water supply, sanitation and health services.
- Inadequate educational and recreational facilities.
- Increase in child labour.
- Encroachment of sub-urban or nearby agricultural land by roads and dwelling houses.
- Inadequate sewerage system.
- Unplanned urban growth making rain water discharge impossible and creating breeding centre for mosquitoes which are responsible for many communicable diseases.
- Domestic and Industrial solid waste disposal polluting ground and surface water as well as land.
- Pollution of atmosphere.
- Cutting down trees and covering land with concrete, building etc.
- Noise pollution.
- Increasing social hazards like hijacking, women trafficking, brothels, drug addiction etc.
- Discontent among city dwellers causing political unrest and halting development process.

POPULATION POLICY

So far we have discussed the consequences of population growth. It's such a broad topic that it's impossible to cover all its cause and effects in a single article. However, from the above discussions, it's clear that population growth is badly affecting world resources and environment. In case of Bangladesh, we have probably crossed the carrying capacity of the country. Yet the population is rapidly increasing. So a sound population policy is an imperative need of the time.

In this regard, there are two opposite views prevalent among the demographers and researchers. First view is that the carrying capacity of the world is limited and direct intervention is essential for stabilization of world population. Otherwise the consequences will be catastrophic. Whereas the other view propagates that technology and economic development will outpace the population growth. According to the theory of demographic transition, though a given society may experience rapid population growth at the transitional stage, yet the population growth will be stabilized at the industrial stage. So, no intervention is required to control the population and emphasis should be given on economic development and social justice. Unfortunately, most of the LDCs are now stuck up at the transitional stage. Death rate is remarkably reduced due to increased health care services with birth rate remaining the same. So population is increasing exponentially. At the same time, food production and over all economic development is seen to be unable to outpace the population growth due to scarcity of natural resources, technical know-how, adequate fund and political instability. Against this backdrop, population control by direct and indirect measure is the only viable alternative. "The importance of reducing high rates of population growth is underscored by such factors as the steadily mounting pressure of human needs on non-renewable and biological resources, environmental pollution and degradation, the impending food crisis in many developing countries, the mounting pressures of migration both within and between countries and unprecedented rates of urban growth. As such, now there is no debate over the goal of population policy—the stabilization of global population within the shortest period possible" (UN 1993 : 29).

The efforts necessary to achieve this goal may be summarized as below :

A. **Family planning measures** which include educational and clinical services for the following :

- birth spacing,
- birth control,
- breast feeding,
- prenatal care,
- supply of contraceptive free of cost or at low cost,
- abortion and sterilization facilities and,
- mother and child care.

B. **Socio-economic measures.** Family planning measures alone are not enough to check the population boom unless coercive measures are adopted like china. India is an example; it started the program in 1952 when its population was 400 million and ended in 1990 with 853 million population. The causes of failure may be attributed to the socio-economic reality of the country. In Bangladesh context, the socio-economic measures that can be taken into consideration to prevent such failure, may include the following :

- Economic reward for adopting family planning programs.
- Economic penalty for non adoption, however, this measure shall have to be applied thoughtfully.
- Campaigning for universal primary education and mass literacy.
- Removing social pressure, both on man and women, for marriage and child bearing.
- Encouraging postponement of marriage or late marriage.
- Campaigning against the religious barrier.
- Introducing old age support scheme.
- Increasing agricultural output.
- Effective land reform.
- Preference of rural development over urban bias development.
- Adopting poverty alleviation program.
- Changing the role of women in society, etc.

CONCLUSION.

It is an established fact that population growth is outpacing the carrying capacity of many developing countries including Bangladesh. It's also established that population growth, natural resources, environment and development are interlinked and integration of different policies is a must for striking a balance between population growth and sustainig the Earth. To achieve the goal of sustainable development we have no alternative but to stabilize population growth and mininize resources depletion and save the environment.

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